

Investigating Stakeholders' Perceptions on the Software Supply Network Model and Requirements Management in the SOLAR Educational Software Ecosystem

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Abstract

Context: Modeling is an important field for software ecosystems (SECO), and software supply network (SSN) is one of the most well-known SECO modeling notations. In a previous study, we proposed an SSN model for a proprietary educational SECO called Online Learning System (SOLAR).

Objective: This work aims to analyze the SSN model of SOLAR SECO from the perceptions of professionals involved in the development of this ecosystem to identify emergent issues and challenges in this ecosystem. As an emergent concern, we investigated requirements management activities in the SOLAR SECO.

Method: We applied a questionnaire and conducted semi-structured interviews with practitioners involved in the SOLAR SECO and qualitatively analyzed their opinions.

Results: We found out that the main problems with the SSN model of SOLAR SECO were related to the lack of technical elements. Moreover,

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we noticed that professionals do not adhere to a specific approach when performing certain requirements management activities.

Conclusions: We found that more requirements documentation to assist in modeling and updating the SSN model is required in SOLAR SECO. As an implication, this work contributes with a methodological procedure to assist researchers and practitioners in modeling and analysis of other SECO cases.

Keywords: Software Supply Network, SSN, Requirements Management, Software Ecosystems, SECO, SECO modeling, SECO analysis

1. Introduction

Software-intensive systems have become increasingly ubiquitous, large, and complex, with dissemination in several application domains and tightly dependent upon different technologies [1]. Currently, such systems are usually centered in a software platform, in which many elements create a socio-technical network (i.e., the interplay between social and technical systems) [2, 3]. The software engineering community has used the ecosystem metaphor to describe those systems usually centered in a software platform and named them as software ecosystems (SECO) [4, 5]. The SECO community has published several secondary studies in the last decade [6, 7, 8] that mentioned the modeling in this context.

Barbosa et al. [6] and Manikas and Hansen [7] considered modeling a strategic topic and an important field in the SECO domain. Jansen et al. [9] highlighted that the lack of information and practices for establishing SECO modeling leads organizations to reinvent methods and tools. Moreover, the lack of SECO modeling support is a great barrier to the evolution of the field toward aiding decision-making in the software industry [5]. According to Pant and Yu [10], modeling can help decision-makers by supporting the representation and reasoning of cooperative strategies in SECO in a structured and systematic manner based on information visualisation.

Jansen et al. [11] stated that there needs to be more studies that contribute to progress toward understanding current modeling practices in the perception of actors who are part of SECO. Sadi and Yu [12] described that studies in real SECO can support understanding how individual modeling techniques assist SECO professionals in their activities (e.g., software development, requirements engineering). According to Jansen et al. [11] and Pant and Yu [10], studies focusing on the main activities and areas of SECO that

involve management practices, architecture, and modeling in real scenarios can fill this gap. In a previous work [5], we performed the modeling of a proprietary educational SECO called Online Learning System (SOLAR), which is based in a virtual learning environment (VLE) designed to enable the creation of a virtual space to support face-to-face or online courses [5]. This modeling activity was based on the Software Supply Network (SSN) notation recommendations described by Boucharas et al. [13] and complemented by Costa et al. [14].

In this previous work, we highlighted the need to analyze the SSN model of SOLAR SECO from the professionals' perceptions involved in the development of SOLAR SECO. According to Sadi and Yu [12], most modeling techniques investigated and applied in the SECO context have not received enough effort regarding experimentation and evaluation in real case studies and by practitioners. The authors also stated that modeling can help the description of the demands for products and services and the interactions between the actors in a SECO. Hence, this work aims to analyze the SSN model of SOLAR SECO from the professionals' perceptions involved in the development of this ecosystem to identify emergent issues and challenges in this ecosystem. As an emergent concern, we investigated requirements management activities in the SOLAR SECO, whose importance was highlighted from/to the model and refers to activities that can benefit from the use of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO. We applied a questionnaire and conducted semi-structured interviews with professionals and end-users to do so.

Based on the results, we found that SOLAR SECO requires further requirements documentation to update its SSN model and that a proper requirements management approach is missing in such an ecosystem. The main contributions of this work are: (i) the definition of a methodological procedure specifically tailored for analyzing an SSN model within a proprietary SECO (SOLAR SECO), which emphasizes specific challenges and dynamics of a SECO; (ii) an analysis of the elements of such an SSN model according to the insights gathered from professionals in a real practical case of a proprietary SECO, addressing the limited access to data that typically characterizes this type of ecosystem; (iii) the identification of the relationship between the analyzed SECO model and requirements management activities within the investigated SECO; (iv) an analysis of the requirements management activities influenced by the elements of the analyzed model; and (v) the identification of findings about an SSN SECO model that extend beyond traditional software or system models, indicating opportunities for further

research in other ecosystems.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the background and related work; Section 3 describes the research method; Section 4 presents the first study; Section 5 presents the second study; Section 6 discusses the results; Section 7 presents limitations; and Section 8 concludes the work with final remarks and future work.

2. Background

This section presents the main definitions to the understanding of this work: SECO and requirements management, SECO modeling, and SOLAR SECO. Moreover, we discuss some related work.

2.1. Software ecosystems and requirements management

SECO is a field of software engineering that aims to understand the dynamics of the platforms-centric software delivery network [15]. Jansen et al. [16] defined SECO “as a set of companies that function as a unit and interact with a shared market for software and services, along with their relationships”. SECO focuses on external or unknown actors contributing to evolving a common software platform across organizational boundaries of an organization. This context changes the traditional value chain, which is organization-centric, towards a supply network in which multiple components developed over different platforms co-exist and affect the acquirer’s businesses [13]. Organizations such as Amazon, Apple, and Google have invested in platforms to engage a critical mass of external developers that help them develop and evolve contributions to these platforms [17].

The Android ecosystem serves as a practical illustration of an SECO. At the core, Google maintains the Android operating system, which forms a platform used by numerous independent developers and device manufacturers. Developers create applications and services that run on Android, extending its functionality. Device manufacturers, such as Samsung and LG, build hardware that integrates with Android, and users interact with these devices and the associated apps [18].

According to Knauss et al. [19], managing the interaction of actors across organizational boundaries and between teams can contribute to the requirements management in SECO. However, requirements management has presented itself as a significant challenge in SECO because organizational boundaries tend to be more open and flexible than in traditional software develop-

ment [20]. Requirements management is an organized process of documenting, analyzing, tracing, prioritizing, controlling changes, and communicating requirements [21]. Its main objective is to ensure consistency between the requirements of the project's products and components [22].

2.2. Software ecosystems modeling

Although there is no consensus regarding how to represent the elements part of a SECO, some modeling techniques have been used to describe SECO, such as Software Process Engineering Meta-model (SPEM) [23], Technical Ecosystem Modeling Notation (TECMO) [24] or Unified Modeling Language (UML) [25]. However, these techniques focus on modeling the software platform but do not deal with the involved actors and the relationships between them [12]. According to Coutinho et al. [5], some SECO elements cannot be represented when applying these modeling notations.

Pant and Yu [10] proposed a model-based approach for analyzing strategic moves in SECO using i^* and game trees that consider the relationships between actors. Moreover, Boucharas et al. [13] proposed standardizing SECO modeling using the SSN strategy, a component of the Software Ecosystem Meta-model (SEM) proposed to describe and analyze SECO. SEM provides a comprehensive view of the ecosystem, addressing not only the interactions between actors (as in the SSN) but also covering other important dimensions, such as 1) source: the origin of components and technologies within the ecosystem; 2) context: external and internal conditions that influence the behavior of actors in the ecosystem, such as regulations, market changes, or new technologies; 3) governance: mechanisms that regulate collaboration and competition between actors; and 4) evolution: how the ecosystem adapts and changes over time, including the entry and exit of actors and the introduction of new products or services [13].

SSN is a series of linked software, hardware, and service organizations cooperating to attend to market demands and represents the structures of software supply chains in SECO [14]. Thus, the main focus of SSN lies in the modeling of business relationships between the members of a SECO in terms of input and output flows between the actors [26]. Costa et al. [14] presented a summary of the SSN components that allow representing the main actors and their interaction in an SECO, as shown in Fig. 1.

The fact that an SSN model shows the interactions between SECO actors can be important for identifying products and services and, consequently,

Figure 1: SSN elements representing the main actors and their interaction in an SECO. Source: [14].

defining new requirements. Moreover, SECO is an environment of collaboration and competition between heterogeneous actors, which demands even more management efforts and requires frequent updates in documentation (i.e., requirements, use cases, and database) to support the modeling stages [12, 27, 28]. Hence, several actors external to a keystone (i.e., organization responsible for sustaining the ecosystem platform) influence the requirements engineering, mainly the requirements management activities in SECO [29, 30, 31].

2.3. SOLAR software ecosystem

SOLAR is a proprietary SECO based in a virtual learning environment (VLE) designed to enable the creation of a virtual space to support face-to-face or online courses [5]. When the ecosystem is centered in a closed environment, where several platforms relate, the ecosystem is known as a proprietary SECO [32]. Proprietary SECO are typically protected by intellectual property (IP) management processes, and the value relates to monetary compensation [8]. Several secondary studies [7, 8, 33] mentioned that the proprietary SECO are little explored in the SECO literature. Manikas [8] explained that proprietary SECO do not necessarily make ecosystem information publicly available.

SOLAR is based on free software with an architecture that can be integrated with other environments. It uses a client-server architecture, and its main software platforms are Ruby on Rails (development technology), several auxiliary graphical environment managers - GEM (components) to automate development, PostgreSQL (database), Nginx (Web Server), Unicorn (Rack Web Server), and Linux (Operating System) [5]. The client side consists of a web browser, HTML and Javascript. The server side comprises the web server, software components, and database [34]. Fig. 2 shows the SOLAR architecture in its web version.

SOLAR consists of the following modules: (i) integration core; (ii) user management and control access; (iii) VLE integrator with the university academic management system; (iv) interactive personal space; (v) evaluation and monitoring; (vi) content authoring tool; (vii) communication tools; (viii) content tools; (ix) administrative tools; (x) course tools; and (xi) collaborative and cooperative tools. SOLAR VLE is mainly available in its web version¹, which is its most common use, currently used in training and classroom courses. There is also the mobile version of SOLAR for iOS and Android, which has reduced functionalities [34].

Surrounding the SOLAR VLE platform, a set of relationships was formed: user relationships, technology supplier relationships, solutions developer relationships, and business relationships. Several systems have been developed over the common technological platform, and many versions and maintenance activities have also emerged. The provision of an API for the construction of solutions for the platform also contributed to the integration and diffusion

¹<https://www.solar.virtual.ufc.br/>

Figure 2: SOLAR architecture. Source [34].

of the SECO. For example, the SOLAR API enables the development of new applications/plugins, which external, internal, or independent customers can use in practice.

The SSN model of SOLAR SECO, introduced in a previous work [5], is based on a reference model for the mobile learning domain, known as mobile learning ecosystems (MLES) [23]. This model maps each element of MLES to SOLAR SECO to identify potential matches [5]. MLES presents elements that define a mobile learning ecosystem. The mapping between the MLES reference model and SOLAR SECO has enabled the identification of improvement and evolution points in the SECO, primarily related to the better documentation of intermediate elements and the deployment of new applications and services within the ecosystem [5]. Fig. 3 presents an SSN model of SOLAR SECO, visualizing the main relationships between the different ecosystem elements. This SSN model provides an initial understanding of SOLAR SECO, contributing to a clearer view of the relationships between the platform, suppliers, clients, and intermediate elements [5].

3. Research method

Based on the results in previous work [5], in which we presented a preliminary study on the SSN model of SOLAR SECO as seen in Section 2.3, we identified the need for further research about it. Thus, we aim to analyze the elements, relationships, and usefulness of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO from the perception of professionals involved in the development of this ecosystem. To do this, we seek to answer the following research question (RQ): “(RQ1) *What are professionals’ perceptions involved in the SOLAR SECO development about the SSN model of SOLAR SECO?*”

After conducting a first study to respond to this RQ, we identified that the SSN model of SOLAR SECO could help in the requirements identification and the identification of the stakeholders involved in the requirements management of SOLAR SECO, contributing to the evolution of the ecosystem. For this reason, we conducted a new study (second study) to analyze stakeholders’ perceptions about requirements management at SOLAR SECO with the following RQ: “(RQ2) *What are the stakeholders’ perceptions of requirements management in the SOLAR SECO?*”

Fig. 4 presents the research method applied in our work. We applied a mixed methods approach based on a questionnaire [35] and semi-structured interviews [36] for data collection. In the following sections, we detail the planning and execution of the studies that are part of this work.

4. Stakeholders’ perception of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO (first study)

This study aimed to analyze the SSN model of SOLAR SECO from the professionals’ perceptions involved in the SOLAR SECO development and was divided into three stages: (i) presentation of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO; (ii) application of a questionnaire; and (iii) conducting semi-structured interviews. We present the details of each step in the following subsections.

Figure 3: SSN model for SOLAR SECO. Source [5].

Figure 4: Overview of the research method.

4.1. Presentation of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO

Initially, to obtain the perceptions of professionals' (e.g., developers/ programmers, managers, consultants, and analysts) on the SSN model of SOLAR SECO (RQ1), we presented a definition of SECO and highlighted the importance of modeling for SECO. Next, we presented the SSN model of SOLAR SECO produced in a previous study (Fig. 3), providing detailed descriptions of each model element. This face-to-face session lasted approximately 1 hour and 30 minutes. After the presentation of the model, together with detailed explanations of its elements, the participants had the opportunity to explore it during their activities in developing SOLAR SECO over a week. At the end of this period, we sent out a questionnaire containing questions related to the model, allowing them to answer individually and share their perceptions.

4.2. Application of a questionnaire

We applied a questionnaire to verify whether professionals could understand the relationships between the different elements of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO and whether the model can support the decision-making process for the management and development of such ecosystem. We considered the guidelines suggested by Pfleeger and Kitchenham [37] to the construction and application of the questionnaire. Thus, we organize this application into three steps: (1) planning, (2) execution, and (3) analysis.

In the *planning* (Step 1), we defined the target audience as professionals (e.g., developers/programmers, managers, consultants, analysts) working on the development of SOLAR SECO. This ecosystem's platform had 14 professionals working on its development by the time the study was carried out.

The questionnaire was available through Google Forms² and was divided into two blocks. In the first block, participants read and agreed/disagreed with the consent form before accessing the questions. In the second block, four questions on the characterization of the participants and three questions on the ecosystem aspects were presented to evaluate the SSN model of SOLAR SECO. At the end of the questionnaire, we included an open field for comments to get further suggestions. Table 1 shows how we divided the questionnaire into closed (Q1, Q2, and Q3) and open (Q4, Q5, Q6, and Q7) questions on demographics and participants’ perceptions.

Table 1: Questionnaire items.

Characterization of participants	
ID	Question
Q1	What is your Academic Degree? <i>Closed question:</i> Undergraduate, MBA (Specialization course), Master’s, PhD
Q2	What is your professional profile? <i>Closed question:</i> Teacher/Researcher, Practitioner (developer, systems analyst, others)
Q3	What kind of software development projects have you participated in? <i>Closed question:</i> SOLAR, Other(s)
Q4	What role(s) do you play (or played) in the SOLAR SECO? <i>Open question</i>
Questions on SECO aspects	
ID	Question
Q5	Based on the presented concepts and the SSN model of SOLAR SECO provided, in your opinion, what technical, business, and social elements do you think were missing? <i>Open question</i>
Q6	Do you think that there is a relationship or element from the SSN model of SOLAR SECO that is confusing or unclear? If so, which and why? <i>Open question</i>
Q7	How could the SSN model of SOLAR SECO support the decision-making process of the management and development of this platform? <i>Open question</i>

In the *execution* (Step 2), we sent out the questionnaire via email to 14 possible participants. We also sent out reminders over time. After the deadline set for data collection, we obtained 14 responses (reaching 100% of the possible participants). We highlight that participants were selected from the list of professionals who are internal to the SOLAR SECO and work on the platform development and evolution. This list was made available by the ecosystem manager.

In the *analysis* (Step 3), we adopted an open coding approach to analyze the answers obtained in the questionnaire [38]. To do so, we organized the

²<https://forms.google.com>

answers in an electronic spreadsheet, enabling two researchers (third and fourth authors) to code the responses. The other researchers who authored this article carried out the reviews. The first three researchers have more than four years of research experience in software engineering, and the other four have more than fifteen years of research experience in software engineering.

During the open coding process, we divided the transcripts into coherent units (sentences or paragraphs) and added **preliminary codes** representing the key answers to which each participant responded. Subsequently, we agreed on a set of **focused codes** that captured the most frequent and relevant findings in the participants’ perceptions. After performing the open coding, axial coding was used to group the codes into **categories**, as described by Charmaz [38]. To do so, the interview excerpts and codes were organized into a document, enabling the researchers to follow up on the main findings based on discussions in several iterative cycles. Thus, we considered 14 valid responses for analysis so that this step allowed us to discuss the results. We highlight applying this questionnaire to the SOLAR SECO professionals was important for selecting interviewees for the following data collection phase. Table 2 shows the example of the coding process for one transcript with resulting codes and categories.

Table 2: Illustration of the questionnaire response coding process.

Unit: “Unit: “I don’t know if it would be the case of considering the development team a kind of supplier or if this would only be appropriate for external entities.” (Participant 12)”		
Preliminary code	Focused code	Category
Consider the development team a supplier	Presence of social elements	Social

4.3. Conducting semi-structured interviews

Based on the analysis of the results obtained from the questionnaire application, we identified an opportunity for a further investigation of whether the SSN model of SOLAR SECO added value to the development and evolution of the ecosystem, which brought new questions about the model. We considered the guidelines adopted in [36] to develop the guide for the semi-structured interviews. We organize the semi-structured interview into three steps: (1) planning, (2) execution, and (3) analysis.

In the *planning* (Step 1), we defined the target audience as professionals involved in developing SOLAR SECO. The application of the questionnaire described previously allowed us to get in touch with such stakeholders. Next, we sent the invitation to the 14 participants in the questionnaire, and three

participants at different levels agreed to participate, making it possible to schedule three semi-structured interviews. Interviewee 1 has 8 years of experience in educational management in SOLAR SECO and has experience in software and hardware infrastructure. Interviewee 2 has 7 years of experience in SOLAR SECO development. Finally, Interviewee 3 has 3 years of experience in SOLAR SECO development. Our interviews were based on a semi-structured guide with open-ended questions. The design of the questions was also carefully considered to provide an explanation for a better understanding from the participants. Before conducting the interviews, we sent out a consent form. Table 3 shows the interview questions.

Table 3: Semi-structured interview questions.

ID	Question
QInter1	Do you believe the SSN model of SOLAR SECO presented can add value to the development team? In what way? Could you give more details?
QInter2	Do you believe that the SSN model of SOLAR SECO presented can help the development team in making management decisions?
QInter3	In your opinion, in which SOLAR SECO development activities could the SSN model of SOLAR SECO be used?
QInter4	In your opinion, can the SSN model of SOLAR SECO help in the identification of new functionalities for SOLAR SECO?

In the *execution* (Step 2), we conducted the online interviews via Google Meet³. Two researchers (third and fourth author) conducted the interviews, and the other researchers reviewed the transcriptions. We requested recording all the content to allow its subsequent complete transcription. However, only one participant authorized the recording of the interview. We obtained the data from the other two participants through manual records (notes) made by the researchers. No maximum time was defined, so the duration of the interviews varied according to the interviewee’s availability and exhaustion of possible answers. All the information provided by the participants was kept confidential based on the consent form.

In the *analysis* (Step 3), we analyzed the data obtained from the interviews. One researcher transcribed the interview of the interviewee, who allowed it to be recorded, to identify similarities between the other interviewees’ responses. The responses from the other interviews were recorded using notes. To analyze the interviews, we read each transcript, marking relevant text passages and recording them in an electronic spreadsheet, thus

³<https://meet.google.com>

Table 4: Illustration of the coding process of the semi-structured interview

Transcript unit: <i>“Considering that we have external developers using our API, as well as teachers, students, coordination, and other SOLAR users, this model can help a new developer on the team to have a visual understanding of the SOLAR target audience. Then, the model can assist in making decisions about which functionality should be prioritized for addition to SOLAR.”</i> (Interviewee 1)		
Preliminary code	Focused code	Category
Visualization of the SOLAR actors	Visualization of the different actors	Positive
Can help prioritize functionalities	Software development steps	Positive

performing an open coding approach inspired by the initial procedure of the Grounded Theory [38]. During the open coding process, we divided the transcripts into coherent units (sentences or paragraphs) and added **preliminary codes** representing the key points each participant talked about. Hence, we ensured the best and most accurate interpretation possible of each interview. Subsequently, we defined a set of **focused codes** that captured the participants’ most frequent and relevant factors. Finally, the results were debated in a group session until they reached a consensus at some point in the discussion. After performing the open coding, we applied axial coding, described by Charmaz [38], to group the codes into **categories**. Table 4 shows examples of two transcripts with resulting codes and categories.

4.4. Results of first study

The first study comprised the application of a questionnaire and semi-structured interviews with professionals involved in the development of SOLAR SECO. Next, we present the results of the first study.

4.4.1. Questionnaire

Regarding the academic degree of the 14 respondents, four hold a Bachelor’s degree, three have an MBA (Specialization course), three have a Master’s degree, and four have a Ph.D. Moreover, five are teachers/researchers, seven are practitioners (developers, systems analysts, or others), and two are teachers/researchers and practitioners (developers, systems analysts, or others). Most participants work as developers, and some work in specific activities (e.g., management, analysis, and accessibility evaluation). A summary of the data is shown in Table 5.

We considered the responses to the open questions Q5 to Q7 to analyze the elements and relationship of the SSN model of SECO SOLAR from

Table 5: Characterization of participants.

Question	Answers	Amount
Academic Degree	Bachelor	4
	MBA (Specialization course) ⁴	3
	Master's	3
	PhD	4
Profile	Teacher/researcher	5
	Practitioner	7
	Both	2
Role in SOLAR SECO	Developer	5
	Systems analyst	1
	Developer and manager	1
	Systems analyst, developer and manager	1
	Interface/Graphic Designer	2
	Accessibility Evaluation	1
	User	1
	Teacher/researcher	1
	Not Answered	1

the perceptions of the professionals involved in the development of SOLAR SECO. Q5 assessed whether any technical, business, and social elements were missing in the provided SSN model of SOLAR SECO. According to the participants, **the main problems with the SSN model of SOLAR SECO were related to the lack of technical elements.** These technical gaps identified by the participants indicate opportunities for developing new products and services. For example, the absence of “text to speech” features suggests developing an add-on in SOLAR SECO. Furthermore, some said that the “representation of integration with other systems” was missing.

“Since ‘Text to speech’ (which does not exist in SOLAR) was cited, it could be integrated and presented in the model.”

[Participant 1]

“The representation of other integrations with other systems (virtual slate, virtual reality, and others) is missing.”

[Participant 11]

“There is a large number of systems that are integrated with SOLAR and I didn’t see them represented in the model. Maybe the closer representation is the Legacy Academic Management System. But I think that it refers the Academic Module.”

[Participant 12]

The participants also mentioned social elements, mainly the lack of representativeness of some actors in the model. A participant who served as a tutor/teacher in SOLAR SECO highlighted the need to improve accessibility of the ecosystem platform so as this can be reflected in the model.

“Other important roles also operate in SOLAR, such as academic secretaries and content developers. I think there should be some connection between the researchers and the development team.”

[Participant 13]

“The very issue about accessibility is a point that needs to be improved in SOLAR (focus on profiled users), to later be represented in the model.”

[Participant 12]

Q6 was related to the clarity of the relationships in the SSN model of SOLAR SECO. Most participants indicated that the relationships present in the SSN model were neither confusing nor missing information. However, one participant cited that some relationships reported in the model, such as the supplier element for Facebook and Twitter, no longer exist or never existed. Moreover, a participant suggested simplifying the nomenclature of one of the elements of the model to improve its understanding.

“There is no longer integration of SOLAR SECO with Facebook, there has never been an integration with Twitter, and I don’t know what ‘Text to Speech’ is. I don’t understand what a legacy academic management system would be.”

[Participant 1]

“Shouldn’t ‘ChatServer Mono’ be renamed to just ‘Chat server’? I think that would be a better name for this element.”

[Participant 6]

For Q7, the majority of responses were positive that the SSN model supports the decision-making process in the management and development of the ecosystem. According to the participants, the model helps understand the interactions in the SOLAR SECO. As an example of statement, one participant reported that:

“The SOLAR SECO model helps to understand all the interactions performed in the system.”

[Participant 2]

In addition, some participants mentioned the SSN model of SOLAR SECO represents aspects of improvement and evolution, assisting in the management, visualization of limitations, and the possibility of inserting new solutions for new functionalities in ecosystems. We present some comments on these aspects next.

“Since the model visually presents the products and services offered by SOLAR SECO, it is possible to identify aspects for improvement, such as integrating SOLAR with social networks, and missing features, such as the environment management module. This gives us a clearer view of SOLAR structure and allows us to define more precise directions for its development and management.”

[Participant 10]

“Understanding the whole scenario through the model makes us think about the limitations and solution possibilities for new features in the system. I was positively surprised by the model.”

[Participant 12]

“I think the SOLAR SECO model helps understand the structure of the main SOLAR components and their interconnections. This makes it easier to understand the design.”

[Participant 14]

4.4.2. Semi-structured interview

Based on the analysis of the responses obtained in the questionnaire, mainly related to Q7, we identified the opportunity to interview some ecosystem professionals to obtain precise information on whether the SSN model of SOLAR SECO adds value to the development and evolution of this ecosystem. Thus, we analyzed the interviewees' answers to open questions QInter1 to QInter4 (Table 3) to understand these aspects.

We sought to obtain the perception of some professionals who work in developing SOLAR SECO about the SSN model of SOLAR SECO. Thus, QInter1 assessed whether the SSN model of SOLAR SECO can add value to the development team. We identified positive and negative aspects of using the SSN model of SOLAR SECO from the analysis of the answers obtained in the interviews. Regarding the positive aspects, the participants mentioned that the SSN model of SOLAR SECO could be helpful in the software development stages. Interviewee 1 stated that the SSN model of SOLAR SECO could help identify the functionalities needed and the actors involved in SOLAR.

“Yes. Looking at the SSN model of SOLAR SECO, I can visualize what functionalities SOLAR needs and who the actors need. In addition, I can understand who is in charge of the administrative side of SOLAR and who is responsible for identifying requirements directly with customers, such as SOLAR coordinators and administrators.”

[Interviewee 1]

QInter2 aimed to identify whether the SSN model of SOLAR SECO could support the development team in making management decisions. We found out that the SSN model of SOLAR SECO assists the analysis of the impact of changes that can occur in the ecosystem. Thus, we identified a hypothesis that can be studied and evaluated in future research: “the different views of the actors can be supported with the use of the SSN model notation, as they help in the analysis of the impact of change and the understanding of mobile technologies or platforms”. The comments of Interviewees 1 and 2 highlighted how the model could help.

“Yes. It allows me to view the impact between the parties, which is very important for a management view.”

[Interviewee 1]

“Through the visualization of the model elements, it would be more didactic to show and convince customers and managers about the changes that can be made in the system because they could see where the change would interfere.”

[Interviewee 2]

Despite the positive aspects, Interviewee 3 reported that developers should be interested in such a model, but they do not care about it culturally. As such, the need for more knowledge on the SECO definition remains a barrier.

“Knowing developers as they are, none of them would be interested in consulting the model. They should be interested, but culturally they don’t care.”

[Interviewee 3]

“A lack of knowledge of the definition of software ecosystems can also contribute to developers’ lack of interest in the model. This is because I myself had never heard of this concept.”

[Interviewee 3]

In QInter3, most responses were positive about the SSN model of SOLAR SECO to support the platform development activities. According to Interviewee 1, the model can be used along with requirements documentation to assess the impact of changes.

“Maintenance and requirements: the impacts of changes can be verified through the requirements (not present in the model) along with the model. Architecture: with requirements, you evaluate the impacts of changes, which can be visually verified on the infrastructure and components represented in the model, such as additions or removals. Development: this is usually the most annoying because many don’t want to consult models. They should know that changing the code has an impact (and they do). For example, the insertion of new operating systems or platforms can greatly impact the ecosystem. If the model is used well, it serves all stages of maintenance and development of the environment. But I think that the model is not good for new projects, starting from scratch.”

[Interviewee 1]

In QInter4, we asked if the model helps identify the SOLAR SECO’s new features (functionalities). According to Interviewees 2 and 3, the model is unsuitable for identifying new features or startup projects because the visualizations show the “size” of the system. Nonetheless, it does not help with opportunities for new features.

“It would not serve to identify functionalities but to use it as a query and evaluate the possible impacts of the changes added to SOLAR.”

[Interviewee 2]

“I don’t think the model is good for new projects, starting from scratch. It would fit to use another way to identify new features and represent them in the model.”

[Interviewee 3]

Another negative aspect reported by the interviewees is the lack of documents related to SOLAR SECO when thinking about modeling and updating its SSN model, such as diagrams of relationships between database entities and requirements documentation. Additionally, the participants noticed the lack of updates of several documents, such as use case specifications, requirements, and updates in the SSN model of SOLAR SECO itself, which leads to a “static” model that doesn’t keep up with changes in the ecosystem. Interviewee 1 highlighted how the lack of documentation can make it difficult for the SOLAR SECO development team to use the model.

“One challenge in updating the model, incorporating the functionalities present in SOLAR, and making it more useful for the team is the need for more documentation. The absence of documents such as requirements, database diagram documentation, and use case specifications is a problem we face at SOLAR. This can result in a “static” model version that doesn’t properly keep up with changes in SOLAR, making it difficult for the development team to update and use the model.”

[Interviewee 1]

5. Stakeholders’ perceptions of requirements management in the SOLAR SECO (second study)

The motivation to carry out this second study was raised from some interviewees’ answers on the fact that the SSN model of SOLAR SECO could help analyze the impacts of changes in ecosystems. Besides, the interviewees reported that the lack of requirements documentation hampers the SSN model update. Thus, we investigated how requirements identification, communication, prioritization, negotiation, change management, and traceability occur in SOLAR SECO. The new round of semi-structured interviews aimed to obtain the stakeholders’ perceptions on requirements management. From the answers of the first study (Section 4), we identified the need for understanding requirements management activities at SOLAR SECO. As such, we prepared a set of interview questions in a second study. We also based the guide of the semi-structured interviews on the interview guidelines adopted in [36]. We organize the semi-structured interview application into three steps: (1) planning, (2) execution, and (3) analysis.

In the *planning* (Step 1), we defined the target audience as SOLAR SECO requirements managers (or similar roles) and users. The ecosystem manager indicated two potential interviewees. Interviewee 1 is the development team coordinator with over 6 years of experience in the platform development and evolution. This person is responsible for receiving customer product and service demands. Interviewee 2 is an experienced user with more than 10 years with the SOLAR platform. The choice of interviewing an experienced user was grounded on the fact that users are the main consumers of products and services and are often responsible for requesting new functionalities.

The interview questions focused on topics related to requirements management activities. Although we approached the questions differently with the two interviewees, we explored the same topics. For the interviewed professional, we asked extra questions on specific aspects of requirements management. This was because the user did not know how requirements management works in the SOLAR SECO, which motivated us to use more accessible language in our questions. Before conducting the interviews, we sent out the consent form. Tables 6 and 7 show how we organized the questions.

In the *execution* (Step 2), we conducted the online interviews from July to August via Google Meet⁵. The first and second authors conducted the

⁵<https://meet.google.com>

Table 6: Questions for the development team coordinator (QD).

ID	Question	Topic
QD1	Is any approach (technique, method, practice, tool etc.) used for requirements management in SOLAR SECO?	Specific aspects of requirements management
QD2	Which actors participate in the requirements management in SOLAR SECO?	Specific aspects of requirements management
QD3	How are requirements identified in SOLAR SECO?	Requirements identification
QD4	What are the main sources of ideas for new products services in SOLAR SECO?	Requirements identification
QD5	Do geographic location, cultural factors, and multiplicity of actors affect the requirements identification in SOLAR SECO?	Requirements identification
QD6	What channels/means do you use to identify and communicate the requirements in SOLAR SECO?	Requirements communication
QD7	How are SOLAR SECO requirements stored?	Requirements communication
QD8	How are requirements prioritized in SOLAR SECO? Is any approach (technique, method, practice, tool etc.) used?	Requirements prioritization
QD9	Are there requirements negotiation in SOLAR SECO? If yes, who is involved in it? How is trading done?	Requirements negotiation
QD10	How do requirements changes occur? Which actors suggest these changes? How are these changes implemented?	Change control
QD11	Are requirements traced in SOLAR SECO? If yes, do you use an approach (technique, method, practice, tool etc.)?	Requirements traceability
QD12	What are the challenges in the requirements management?	Requirements management challenges

Table 7: Questions for experienced SOLAR SECO user (QU).

ID	Question	Topic
QU1	Does the SOLAR SECO team involve you when defining products/services?	Requirements identification
QU2	How do you submit requests for new products/services or bug fixes in SOLAR SECO?	Requirements identification
QU3	Are the means of communication (meetings, SOLAR chat, and email) used at SOLAR SECO to receive your demands sufficient?	Requirements communication
QU4	Could other channels/means of communication be used/made available on SOLAR SECO? Which?	Requirements communication
QU5	Do you classify your demands in terms of priority or urgency for the implementation to be carried out?	Requirements prioritization
QU6	When you requested a product/service demand, was there any discussion with the SOLAR SECO team for the implementation to be carried out?	Requirements negotiation
QU7	How do you track the status of your demand and the SOLAR SECO team's definitions to implement it?	Change control and requirements traceability
QU8	Is it possible to improve the ways to request, follow up, and discuss your demands in SOLAR SECO? How?	Requirements management challenges

interviews. Both interviewees authorized recording all the content to allow transcription. Similar to the first study, no maximum time was defined, so the duration of the interviews varied according to the interviewee’s availability and exhaustion of possible answers. All the information provided by the participants was kept confidential based on the consent form.

In the *analysis* (Step 3), we analyzed the data obtained from the interviews. To support the analysis and transcription, we used the Card Sorting method presented by Spencer [39]. As such, the same two researchers who conducted the interviews transcribed it to identify answers to the RQ2. Then, they read the interview transcripts, marked relevant text excerpts, and divided them into coherent units (sentences or paragraphs). The other researchers reviewed the results of the analysis. We highlight that all interviews were carried out in Portuguese, and the transcriptions presented in this article were translated into English.

5.1. Results of second study

To identify specific aspects of requirements management, we analyzed the answers to QD1 and QD2. According to the development team coordinator, the SOLAR SECO team does not adopt any specific approach (technique, tool, method etc.) for requirements management. Although no specific technique is adopted, the development team coordinator emphasizes that the professionals employ “generic” requirements management practices, with a team member with experience in requirements management for managing all requirements throughout the platform development.

“No specific technique is used for requirements management. However, a specific person with experience in requirements management is responsible for filtering and managing the requirements, and this part has the participation of the university management.”

[Development team coordinator]

QD3, QD4, and QD5 aimed to understand how requirements identification occurs in SOLAR SECO according to the developers’ perspective. We identified that email is the communication channel for requirements identification (QD3) and that the requirements arise from the SECO keystone’s

internal and external actors (QD4). The development team coordinator mentioned that geographical location, cultural factors, and number of actors do not affect requirements identification in SOLAR SECO (QD5).

“The sources of requirements come from management who may pick up requirements from other departments in the university, through external partnerships, by faculty, by other users (students) and by the developers themselves who suggest new requirements, so several actors are involved.”

[Development team coordinator]

“It is not challenging to identify requirements with clients. I don’t think that geographical location, the number of actors, and their culture make it difficult to identify requirements.”

[Development team coordinator]

QU1 and QU2 focused on obtaining the user’s perspective on requirements identification. The user usually communicates with the development team via email to submit their requirements. In addition, the user can evaluate SOLAR SECO new features and interface utilizing a questionnaire.

“Usually, the SOLAR maintainers publish a questionnaire to get the user’s perceptions of a feature or evaluate the interface. These means of evaluating SOLAR have contributed a lot to improving the environment. In addition, I use email to communicate with the team and send demands.”

[Experienced SOLAR SECO user]

In QD6 and QD7, we identified points related to the requirements communication and storage. We identified that there is no central repository to store the requirements. Spreadsheets, project management tools, and bug-tracking tools often store requirements.

“The requirements are not stored in a central platform; they are all organized in worksheets that are automatically generated through the forms received from the users. The Pivotal Tracker tool and Trello tool are used to store new and old requirements.”

[Development team coordinator]

We asked the experienced SOLAR SECO user if the communication channels were sufficient to send their demands (QU3) and if the ecosystem could make other channels available (QU4). The experienced user described that the communication channels are sufficient but suggested the inclusion of a chatbot to make communication more automated.

“I consider that the communication channels are sufficient, as I have direct contact with those responsible for the SOLAR SECO development team. However, those who do not have this direct contact may find it difficult to inform their demands.”

[Experienced SOLAR SECO user]

In QD8, we got information about requirements prioritization. We identified that the SOLAR SECO development team does not apply any specific approach to this activity. However, they use urgency and deadline factors that affect decision-making in requirements prioritization. We also ask the experienced user whether they inform the development team about the priority of their requirements when requesting them (QU5). This user replied that he/she does not know the priority of his/her demand. This meets the development team coordination’s answer.

“The requirements prioritization considers the urgency of the demand. If the demand can cause the platform to stop working, the requirement is prioritized. Another factor that is considered is deadlines. If a department requests a feature and defines a deadline, these requirements are prioritized automatically.”

[Development team coordinator]

QD9 focused on requirements negotiation in SOLAR SECO. We identified that the requirements negotiation occurs in the requirements identification. After receiving demands, the platform development team communicates with the users to negotiate the requirements. To obtain information on the requirements negotiation, we asked the experienced user if he/she was involved in this negotiation (QU6). He/she confirmed his/her participation on the requirements negotiation, as informed by the development team coordinator.

“The requirements negotiation occurs early in the requirements identification. We talk with users or other actors. We do an interview to find out what this stakeholder specifically wants in the implementation of their demand. We document all definitions.”

[Development team coordinator]

QD10 sought to identify how requirements change control and requirements traceability occur in SOLAR SECO. We found out that the different SOLAR SECO actors and the development team requested requirements changes. After requesting a change, the development team analyzes the request and outlines a strategy to implement it. However, according to the development team coordinator, no specific approach is used to perform requirements traceability (QD11). Furthermore, according to the experienced user, there is no way for tracking the status of his/her request (QU7).

“The changes in requirements are identified during the project. The demands for changes are influenced by customers/users or by the SOLAR SECO development team. When we receive a change request, we analyze the impact with the team and come up with a strategy to implement the change.”

[Development team coordinator]

“The team does not use a technique for requirements traceability. The closest to requirements traceability is to follow which communication channel requirements came from and who was the actor who requested the demand.”

[Development team coordinator]

Regarding the challenges of requirements management at SOLAR SECO (QD12 and QU8), according to the development team coordinator, the requirements prioritization must consider more factors than those presented in the QD8 response. There is a difficulty related to requirements communication, negotiation, and clarification. According to the development team coordinator, users need to understand that implementing functionalities requires planning and time to do so. For the experienced user, the challenge refers to the lack of feedback on implementing their demands by the development team.

“The requirements management difficulties in SOLAR are related to requirements prioritization and impact analysis of requirements changes. For this, it is necessary to consider what is being done and what should be done next. Requirements communication with the end-users is one of the challenges. In addition, clarifying the functionalities precisely is a challenge too because often the end-users do not understand that not every demand is made in a short time or on time.”

[Development team coordinator]

“As a user, a communication channel to receive feedback on the requested demands would be a way to improve and have more effective communication between the SOLAR team and the user.”

[Experienced SOLAR SECO user]

Overall, we acquired the stakeholders' perception of how requirements management activities are conducted in the SOLAR SECO. We noticed that professionals do not adhere to a specific approach when performing certain activities; instead, they rely on practices grounded in their experience in requirements management. This encompasses assigning a specific role to an individual with expertise in requirements management, employing urgency and deadline criteria for requirements prioritizing, and requirements traceability through communication channels without an approach to tracking.

6. Discussion

The main goal of this study was to analyze the SSN model of SOLAR SECO to identify emergent issues and challenges in this ecosystem from stakeholders' perceptions. First, we collected professionals' perceptions of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO involved in the platform development process using a questionnaire and semi-structured interviews (first study). These professionals highlighted that the SSN model could help analyze the impacts of changes in ecosystems. For this reason, we also investigated stakeholders' perceptions of requirements management activities in the SOLAR SECO through semi-structured interviews (second study).

The results obtained in the first study pointed out some positive and negative aspects of the SSN model of SOLAR SECO. According to our findings, the SSN model provides insights for identifying new products and services and analyzing the impacts of changes. This aligns with the work of Knauss et al. [30], who state that integrating a new contribution into the ecosystem platform leads to the emergence of new functionalities and can generate new interactions with existing contributions in the general context. Our study further illustrates that deciding which contributions to implement in an ecosystem is not trivial, as it requires carefully aligning several requirements with the ecosystem's context and the stakeholders' critical interests.

Some professionals involved in developing SOLAR SECO platform mentioned that there were relationships or elements of the SSN model that were confusing or unclear to them. However, we noticed that some of these professionals did not know all the elements of the SSN model or recognized them by different nomenclature. This highlights the importance of a shared understanding within the ecosystem. According to Sadi and Yu [12], ecosystem modeling can enhance the understanding of a SECO and serve as a means to help professionals establish a common vocabulary (terminology) to align their

perceptions. By fostering a clearer communication framework, professionals can navigate the complexities of the SSN model and its elements.

Regarding the data obtained from the semi-structured interviews in the first study, we identified several positive comments about how the SSN model of SOLAR SECO supports software developers. Some interviewees noted that the model provides valuable insights into the impact of changes within the ecosystem. This aligns with the perspectives shared by Pant and Yu [10], who assert that SECO modeling can aid software developers and organizations in decision-making by facilitating the representation and reasoning of cooperative strategies within the SECO context in a structured and systematic manner. Therefore, fostering awareness among stakeholders about the benefits of modeling is crucial for enhancing the development process in such environments. By recognizing the value of models, stakeholders can leverage them to improve collaboration and efficiency in their development efforts.

In the second study, we conducted semi-structured interviews based on the results from the first study. We found that the professionals developing SOLAR SECO have not yet formalized a requirements management process. However, this activity is managed by a specific actor within the ecosystem (the development team coordinator) and involves participation from other stakeholders, including managers and users. An experienced SOLAR SECO user confirmed this situation during the interview. This aligns with the observations made by Knauss et al. [19], who note that requirements management in SECO tends to be informal, characterized by overlapping practices and the use of informalisms [40]. The informal nature of these processes may hinder effective collaboration and decision-making, highlighting the need for a more structured approach to requirements management within SECO [41].

In SOLAR SECO, closed communication channels (e.g., email and platform chat) serve as the primary means for identifying and communicating requirements. The experienced user interviewed indicated that these communication channels are sufficient for sharing demands. However, this perspective contrasts with the findings of Knauss et al. [19], who emphasize that open communication channels facilitate the flow of information among users, customers, and developers in such environments. Open channels promote transparent communication among stakeholders, which is essential for effectively managing requirements. In SECO, achieving a high level of transparency in requirements communication is crucial to address the challenge of representing a large and heterogeneous set of stakeholders [19]. While closed channels may currently be utilized, fostering more open communication could

enhance collaboration and understanding within the SECO community.

Although there is a defined number of communication channels for identifying requirements, the actual requirements can be found across many repositories, as noted by the development team coordinator. This interviewee indicated that requirements arise from requests made by various actors within the organization managing SOLAR (students, teachers, and technicians) as well as from external partnerships that propose new requirements. This situation mirrors the findings of Vegendla et al. [42], who conducted a systematic mapping study and found that requirements are often stored in multiple decentralized repositories and originate from a diverse set of actors, potentially belonging to different companies within the SECO context. The decentralized nature of requirements management in SOLAR SECO underscores the complexity of effectively tracking and addressing stakeholder needs.

Regarding the challenges in requirements management, the SOLAR SECO development team coordinator perceives that prioritization and communication are significant issues. According to the experienced user interviewed, the primary challenge is the lack of effective communication needed to follow up and receive feedback on the status of requests sent to the development team. Soltani and Knauss [28] support this sentiment, who highlights that communication remains a critical challenge in requirements management across the general SECO context. The difficulties in maintaining clear communication and prioritizing requirements hinder the development process and impact stakeholders' ability to collaborate effectively, underscoring the need for improved communication strategies within SOLAR SECO.

Based on the results, we found out that the SSN model of SOLAR SECO can contribute to identifying new possibilities for integration as well as visualization of the impacts of changes that may occur in the ecosystem platform. However, the lack of adoption of specific techniques or practices for requirements management contributes to the lack of updating of the ecosystem documentation artifacts, which can compromise the model updating, according to participants. Sadi and Yu [12] highlighted that SECO modeling should enable the visual representation of relationships between contributors in the ecosystem. According to Boucharas et al. [43], the requirements engineering, as well as requirements management, may benefit from modeling techniques when properly balancing flexibility for capturing several user needs with formal rigidity required for model analysis and transformations as well as high-level abstraction with information richness.

7. Threats to validity

We recognize that questionnaires and semi-structured interviews can introduce biases and contain ambiguous and incomplete questions, even with all the precautions and attention from the researchers. Regarding the research method, the limitations are typical of qualitative studies [44], particularly in generalizing the results. Regarding the questionnaire sample, we highlight that we obtained 100% of the responses from the professionals involved in the development of the SOLAR SECO platform at the time of the study. Regarding the sample of the semi-structured interviews, we emphasize that we conducted interviews with three SOLAR SECO professionals (first study). Moreover, we interviewed the professional responsible for receiving demands for products and services in the SOLAR SECO and an experienced user (second study). The number of respondents could be more expressive, as it affects the degree of generalization. However, they represent a sample of experts with valuable experience and a relevant potential to contribute with opinions. We also identified the following threats to validity:

External validity refers to the generalization of the study findings. The qualitative analysis based on the open questions of the questionnaire and semi-structured interviews is focused on a real SECO case, and we do not intend to generalize its results but provide indications for future studies in other cases. We performed a qualitative analysis to help in the understanding of aspects of the research whose investigation could be hardly developed via quantitative methods. We do not claim that the SOLAR SECO stakeholders' perceptions are representative or generalized. However, even using this case as a specific case to be investigated, the perception of modeling and requirements management can provide an understanding about its manifestation in other ecosystems.

Internal validity refers to the factors that cause the outcomes but are not in control or measurable. The research structure and questions may have introduced some threats to internal validity. All authors reviewed the questionnaire questions prior to executing both studies. We improved the questions based on the feedback we received from each author. Moreover, we are aware of an inherent threat to questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, given that answers refer to participants' subjective views and can be biased.

Construct validity refers to the relation between the concepts behind the experimentation and observations. The structure and content of the ques-

tionnaire and semi-structured interview questions could be potential threats to the construct validity of the study. A previous questionnaire evaluation mitigates the construct validity threats carried out through a pilot with 2 independent researchers/professionals. We also know that the design of the questionnaire and the semi-structured interviews may not have been clear or sufficient to ensure the best quality of responses. As we interviewed the participants, we repeated and explained the questions to avoid misunderstandings.

Conclusion validity refers to reaching correct conclusions based on rigorous and repeatable treatment. The semi-structured interviews were recorded and transcribed without changes and were analyzed from a method already applied in other studies with the same objective. More than one researcher participated in the interviews to take notes on the main points and throw out all the doubts regarding the participant's answers, especially when the interviewees did not allow the interview recording.

8. Final remarks

In this work, analyzed the SSN model of SOLAR SECO from the professionals' perceptions involved in the development of this ecosystem to identify emergent issues and challenges in this ecosystem. As an emergent concern, we investigated requirements management activities in the SOLAR SECO. We found out that the main problems with the SSN model of SOLAR SECO were related to the lack of technical elements. Moreover, we noticed that professionals do not adhere to a specific approach when performing certain activities; instead, they rely on practices grounded in their experience in requirements management. This encompasses assigning a specific role to an individual with expertise in requirements management, employing urgency and deadline criteria for requirements prioritizing, and requirements traceability through communication channels without a particular approach.

A negative point identified in this research refers to the fact that the need for updated documents on SOLAR SECO, such as database (entity-relationship diagrams) and requirements documentation, affects the modeling and updating of the ecosystem. We also identified no formal requirements management process in SOLAR SECO. Finally, we found that the SSN model could assist with several requirements management activities, including identifying changes to requirements and analyzing the impacts of those changes based on the responses we received.

Our results have implications for researchers and practitioners in the field. Based on SECO modeling, it is possible to define effectively the formal characteristics and elements of a SECO. Moreover, other modeling notations and methods can be explored and compared to support requirements management. Based on the results of this work, practitioners managing real SECO can use this work as a guide to check similar positive and negative aspects compared to SOLAR SECO or to identify different aspects that affect the SECO platform development. As such, practitioners can analyze their practices and get insights to monitor their SECO possibly.

Future work can be pointed out from the results: i) investigate needs and barriers for SECO modeling from other studies in different types of real SECO in industry, as well as relate them to other software development activities; ii) formalize a specific requirements management process in SOLAR SECO based on a case study and interview developers to identify the perceived improvements and its effect on the SOLAR SECO model over time; and iii) perform a more detailed examination of how frequent requirements changes affect SECO modeling and how modeling techniques can help to visualize such changes and guide relevant decisions over time in real SECO.

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References

- [1] J. Bosch, Software ecosystems – implications for strategy, business model and architecture, in: 2011 15th International Software Product Line Conference, 2011, pp. 351–351. doi:10.1109/SPLC.2011.10.
- [2] G. K. Hanssen, T. Dybå, Theoretical foundations of software ecosystems, in: 4th International Workshop on Software Ecosystems (IWSECO), in Conjunction with the 3rd International Conference on Software Business (ICSOB), CEUR-WS.org, 2012, pp. 6–17.
- [3] A. W. Abreu, E. F. Coutinho, Motivating web and blockchain application modeling, in: 2020 IEEE International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (ICSA-C), 2020, pp. 110–113. doi:10.1109/ICSA-C50368.2020.00029.
- [4] D. Dhungana, I. Groher, E. Schludermann, S. Biffl, Software ecosystems vs. natural ecosystems: Learning from the ingenious mind of nature, in: Fourth European Conference on Software Architecture: Companion Volume, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2010, pp. 96—102. doi:10.1145/1842752.1842777.

- [5] E. F. Coutinho, D. Viana, R. Santos, An exploratory study on the need for modeling software ecosystems: The case of solar seco, in: 2017 IEEE/ACM 9th International Workshop on Modelling in Software Engineering (MiSE), Buenos Aires, Argentina, 2017, pp. 47–53. doi:10.1109/MiSE.2017.3.
- [6] O. Barbosa, R. P. Santos, C. Alves, C. Werner, S. Jansen, A systematic mapping study on software ecosystems from a three-dimensional perspective, in: S. Jansen, S. Brinkkemper, M. Cusumano (Eds.), *Software Ecosystems: Analyzing and Managing Business Networks in the Software Industry*, Cheltenham, UK, 2013, pp. 59–81. doi:10.4337/9781781955628.00011.
- [7] K. Manikas, K. M. Hansen, Software ecosystems – a systematic literature review, *Journal of Systems and Software* 86 (5) (2013) 1294–1306. doi:10.1016/j.jss.2012.12.026.
- [8] K. Manikas, Revisiting software ecosystems research: A longitudinal literature study, *Journal of Systems and Software* 117 (2016) 84–103. doi:10.1016/j.jss.2016.02.003.
- [9] S. Jansen, M. Cusumano, K. M. Popp, Managing software platforms and ecosystems, *IEEE Software* 36 (3) (2019) 17–21. doi:10.1109/MS.2019.2891795.
- [10] V. Pant, S. Eric, Understanding strategic moves and reciprocity on software ecosystems: A strategic modeling approach., in: S. Hyrnsalmi, A. Suominen, C. Jud, J. Bosch (Eds.), *9th International Workshop on Software Ecosystems (IWSECO)*, Espoo, Finland, 2017, pp. 28–42.
- [11] S. Jansen, E. Handoyo, C. Alves, Scientists’ needs in modelling software ecosystems, in: *2015 European Conference on Software Architecture Workshops*, New York, NY, USA, 2015. doi:10.1145/2797433.2797479.
- [12] M. Sadi, E. Yu, Designing software ecosystems: How can modeling techniques help?, in: K. Gaaloul, R. Schmidt, S. Nurcan, S. Guerreiro, Q. Ma (Eds.), *Enterprise, Business-Process and Information Systems Modeling*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2015, pp. 360–375. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-19237-6_23.

- [13] V. Boucharas, S. Jansen, S. Brinkkemper, Formalizing software ecosystem modeling, in: 1st International Workshop on Open Component Ecosystems, New York, NY, USA, 2009, p. 41–50. doi:10.1145/1595800.1595807.
- [14] G. Costa, F. Silva, R. Santos, C. Werner, T. Oliveira, From applications to a software ecosystem platform: An exploratory study, in: Fifth International Conference on Management of Emergent Digital EcoSystems, New York, NY, USA, 2013, p. 9–16. doi:10.1145/2536146.2536159.
- [15] R. Santos, D. Viana, Software ecosystems in the development of web, social networks and multimedia platforms, in: 22nd Brazilian Symposium on Multimedia and the Web, New York, NY, USA, 2016, pp. 21–22. doi:10.1145/2976796.2988220.
- [16] S. Jansen, A. Finkelstein, S. Brinkkemper, A sense of community: A research agenda for software ecosystems, in: 31st International Conference on Software Engineering-Companion Volume, Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2009, pp. 187–190. doi:10.1109/ICSE-COMPANION.2009.5070978.
- [17] A. Fontão, S. Cleger-Tamayo, I. Wiese, R. Santos, A. Dias-Neto, A developer relations (devrel) model to govern developers in software ecosystems, *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process* 35 (5) (2023) e2389. doi:10.1002/smr.2389.
- [18] M. Xu, C. Song, Y. Ji, M.-W. Shih, K. Lu, C. Zheng, R. Duan, Y. Jang, B. Lee, C. Qian, S. Lee, T. Kim, Toward engineering a secure android ecosystem: A survey of existing techniques, *ACM Comput. Surv.* 49 (2) (Aug. 2016). doi:https://doi.org/10.1145/2963145.
- [19] E. Knauss, A. Yussuf, K. Blincoe, D. Damian, A. Knauss, Continuous clarification and emergent requirements flows in open-commercial software ecosystems, *Requirements Engineering* 23 (1) (2018) 97–117. doi:10.1007/s00766-016-0259-1.
- [20] D. Damian, J. Linåker, D. Johnson, T. Clear, K. Blincoe, Challenges and strategies for managing requirements selection in software ecosystems, *IEEE Software* 38 (6) (2021) 76–87. doi:10.1109/MS.2021.3105044.

- [21] ISO/IEC/IEEE29148, Iso/iec/ieee international standard - systems and software engineering – life cycle processes – requirements engineering, ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018(E) (2018) 1–104doi:<https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2018.8559686>.
- [22] C. Hood, S. Wiedemann, S. Fichtinger, U. Pautz, Requirements management: The interface between requirements development and all other systems engineering processes, Springer Science & Business Media, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2007. doi:10.1007/978-3-540-68476-3.
- [23] O. Pettersson, M. Svensson, D. Gil, J. Andersson, M. Milrad, On the role of software process modeling in software ecosystem design, in: Fourth European Conference on Software Architecture: Companion Volume, New York, NY, USA, 2010, p. 103–110. doi:10.1145/1842752.1842778.
- [24] C. Seidl, U. Aßmann, Towards modeling and analyzing variability in evolving software ecosystems, in: 7th International Workshop on Variability Modelling of Software-Intensive Systems, New York, NY, USA, 2013. doi:10.1145/2430502.2430507.
- [25] J. Van Angeren, J. Kabbedijk, S. Jansen, K. M. Popp, A survey of associate models used within large software ecosystems, in: S. Jansen, J. Bosch, P. Campbell, F. Ahmed (Eds.), Third International Workshop on Software Ecosystems, Brussels, Belgium, 2011, pp. 27–39.
- [26] E. Handoyo, S. Jansen, S. Brinkkemper, Software ecosystem modeling: The value chains, in: Fifth International Conference on Management of Emergent Digital EcoSystems, MEDES '13, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2013, p. 17–24. doi:10.1145/2536146.2536167.
- [27] E. Knauss, D. Damian, A. Knauss, A. Borici, Openness and requirements: Opportunities and tradeoffs in software ecosystems, in: Proceedings of the IEEE 22nd International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE), Karlskrona, Sweden, 2014, pp. 213–222. doi:10.1109/RE.2014.6912263.
- [28] M. Soltani, E. Knauss, Cross-organizational challenges of requirements engineering in the autosar ecosystem: An exploratory case study,

- in: 2015 IEEE Fifth International Workshop on Empirical Requirements Engineering (EmpiRE), Ottawa, ON, Canada, 2015, pp. 41–48. doi:10.1109/EmpiRE.2015.7431306.
- [29] S. Fricker, Specification and analysis of requirements negotiation strategy in software ecosystems, in: International Workshop on Software Ecosystems (IWSECO'09), Falls Church, VA, USA, 2009, pp. 19–33. doi:10.5167/uzh-28289.
- [30] A. Knauss, A. Borici, E. Knauss, D. Damian, Towards understanding requirements engineering in it ecosystems, in: 2012 Second IEEE International Workshop on Empirical Requirements Engineering (EmpiRE), Chicago, IL, USA, 2012, pp. 33–36. doi:10.1109/EmpiRE.2012.6347679.
- [31] R. P. Santos, C. M. L. Werner, On the impact of software ecosystems in requirements communication and management, in: J. Castro, F. Alencar, M. Lucena, G. C. Filho (Eds.), Requirements Engineering@Brazil 2013, Vol. 1005 of CEUR Workshop Proceedings, CEUR-WS.org, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2013.
- [32] L. A. Costa, A. Fontão, R. Santos, Toward proprietary software ecosystem governance strategies based on health metrics, IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management 69 (6) (2022) 3589–3603. doi:10.1109/TEM.2021.3116531.
- [33] C. Alves, J. Oliveira, S. Jansen, Understanding governance mechanisms and health in software ecosystems: A systematic literature review, in: S. Hammoudi, M. Śmiałek, O. Camp, J. Filipe (Eds.), Enterprise Information Systems, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2018, pp. 517–542. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-93375-7_24.
- [34] E. Coutinho, C. Bezerra, A study on dynamic aspects variability in the solar educational software ecosystem, Journal of the Brazilian Computer Society 26 (1) (2020) 1–19. doi:10.1186/s13173-020-00103-5.
- [35] B. Kitchenham, S. Pfleeger, Personal Opinion Surveys, Springer London, London, 2008, pp. 63–92. doi:10.1007/978-1-84800-044-5_3.
- [36] S. Hove, B. Anda, Experiences from conducting semi-structured interviews in empirical software engineering research, in: 11th IEEE Interna-

- tional Software Metrics Symposium (METRICS'05), Como, Italy, 2005, pp. 10 pp.–23. doi:10.1109/METRICS.2005.24.
- [37] S. L. Pfleeger, B. A. Kitchenham, Principles of survey research: Part 1: Turning lemons into lemonade, *SIGSOFT Softw. Eng. Notes* 26 (6) (2001) 16–18. doi:10.1145/505532.505535.
- [38] K. Charmaz, *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*, Sage Publications, London, 2006.
- [39] D. Spencer, *Card sorting: Designing usable categories*, Rosenfeld Media, New York, 2009.
- [40] W. Scacchi, Understanding requirements for open source software, in: K. Lyytinen, P. Loucopoulos, J. Mylopoulos, B. Robinson (Eds.), *Design Requirements Engineering: A Ten-Year Perspective*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 467–494. doi:10.1007/978-3-540-92966-6_27.
- [41] P. Malcher, E. Silva, D. Viana, R. Santos, What do we know about requirements management in software ecosystems?, *Requirements Engineering* 28 (4) (2023) 567–593. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-023-00407-w.
- [42] A. Vegendla, A. N. Duc, S. Gao, G. Sindre, A systematic mapping study on requirements engineering in software ecosystems, *Journal of Information Technology Research (JITR)* 11 (1) (2018) 49–69. doi:10.4018/JITR.2018010104.
- [43] A. Moreira, G. Mussbacher, J. Araújo, P. Sánchez, Theme section on model-driven requirements engineering, *Software and Systems Modeling* 21 (6) (2022) 2109–2112. doi:10.1007/s10270-022-01055-4.
- [44] B. A. Kitchenham, D. Budgen, P. Brereton, *Evidence-based software engineering and systematic reviews*, Vol. 4, CRC Press, London, 2015.